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SWOT ANALYSIS OF ERICULTURE

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ABSTRACT

The reduction of rural poverty continues to be a paramount goal of the developing countries like India. So far various strategies (Sericulture is most appropriate out of them) have been pursued to address this concern and the rural employment creation is one of the major aspects. In India Sericulture is essentially village based industry providing employment to a sizable section of a population. Sericulture is not only a traditional, but also a living culture. It is an agro based labour intensive and commercially attractive economic activity falling under the cottage and small scale sector. India is the largest producer of Eri silk in the world as 96% of Eri silk is produced in India of the total Eri silk produced in the world (Rajesh Kumar and S.K.Gangwar 2010). Ericulture cannot progress unless it is thought out, planned and implemented in total perspective of the nation. No doubt, the central as well as the state government have their agencies in many places of the country and have been doing something. The aim of my SWOT analysis is to develop work plan for my research that takes into consideration many different internal and external factors and maximizes the potential of the strengths and opportunities while seeking minimize the impact of the weaknesses and threats.

Keywords:

SWOT, Ericulture, Strengths, Opportunities, Weaknesses and Threats.

INTRODUCTION

The reduction of rural poverty continues to be a paramount goal of the developing countries like India. So far various strategies (Sericulture is most appropriate out of them) have been pursued to address this concern and the rural employment creation is one of the major aspects. In India Ericulture is essentially village based industry providing employment to a sizable section of a population. Sericulture is not only a traditional, but also a living culture. It is an agro based labour intensive and commercially attractive economic activity falling under the cottage and small scale sector. It particularly suit rural-based farmers, entrepreneurs and artisans. The present global scenario clearly indicates the enormous opportunities for the Indian silk Industry, because

- The India is the second largest producer of silk in the world. According to FAO estimates, the world raw silk production for the year 2010 was 164971 Tonnes in Asia and especially in Eastern Asia. In India, annual silk production is around 19,000 Tonnes 2010 (Styliani Kalantzi *et al.*, 2013).
- The India has the unique distinction of being only country producing all the five commercially traded varieties of natural silks namely Mulberry, Eri, Muga, Tropical Tasar and Temperate Tasar.

- The India has a distinct advantage of practicing sericulture all through the year, yielding a stream of about 4-6 crops as a result of its tropical climate.

India is the largest producer of Eri silk in the world as 96% of Eri silk is produced in India of the total Eri silk produced in the world (Rajesh Kumar and S.K.Gangwar 2010). Eri silk production in India 2007-08 was 1530 tones this made up 73% of the total Vanya silk production of 2075 tonnes. Eri silk is produced by Eri silkworm (*Philosamia ricini*) is multivoltine, holometabolus, poly phagous, non-mulberry, completely domesticated silkworm. Eri silkworm *Philosamia ricini* (Lepidoptera: Saturniidae) has a unique distinction among other three silkworms of having its potential host, the castor (*Ricinus communis*) an important agricultural oil bearing crop. (Sundarraaj *et al.*, 1972; Jolly *et al.*, 1979; Dayashankar, 1982; Pandey, 1995; Reddy *et al.*, 1998; and Debaraj *et al.*, 2002.) The Castor plant can be grown on semi arable, degraded soil, grown on wasteland and also grown in rain fed condition.

Eri culture cannot progress unless it is thought out, planned and implemented in total perspective of the nation. No doubt, the central as well as the state government have their agencies in many places of the country and have been doing something. But there is a lack of right approach. The nation may be divided into specific regions according to climatic conditions and technology be developed, suited to a particular region. Sericulture is an important agro-based, labour intensive and export oriented cottage industry. The 29.2% of the total land (52.33 lack hector) of Ujjain District is irrigated. 57,000 acre of the land comes under 41 command areas of the irrigation project and is therefore secured irrigated. In order to expand the Mulberry silk production centers were opened in the district of Ujjain.

The first Sericulture Mulberry silk center was opened in 1986-87 at Barnagar (silk center Molana) a Tehsil of Ujjain. Silk centers are now working at Ghatia (Silk center Malyakhedi), Khachraud (Kanchankhedi), Mahidpur (Kajikhedi and Arniya), and Ujjain (sahebkhedi, Undasa, Chandesari, Chandesara) Tehsil also. Agro climatic condition of Ujjain, Madhya Pradesh is congenial for Eri food plant cultivation and Eri silkworm rearing. Rural areas can be tapped to enhance Eri culture rearing, production and other activities.

The aim of my SWOT analysis is to develop work plan for my research that takes into consideration many different internal and external factors and maximizes the potential of the strengths and opportunities while seeking minimize the impact of the weaknesses and threats.

SWOT ANALYSIS OF ERICULTURE

SWOT analysis is a structured planning method used to evaluate the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats involved in a project or research work. SWOT analysis aims to identify the key internal (the strengths and weaknesses internal to the organization) and external factors (the opportunities and threats presented by the environment external to the organization) seen as important to achieving an objective.

Strength: –

1. Sericulture Research Institutes through their technical development have provided super quality of seed.
2. The silk is produced 30-40% less than the demand of national & international level.
3. Eri silkworm is hardy and Nonviolence (Ahinsa) silk.
4. Eri silk is poor person's silk (cost of production is very less than other silk).
5. Eri silk is coarse, fine, dense, strong and durable than other silk. It is suitable for Shawls, Jackets, and Blankets because of thermal properties.

6. Baby dresses are also made from Eri silk because of its soft texture and moisture absorbent qualities.
7. Eri silk worms are sturdier than other silk worms.
8. Castor leaves are available throughout the year and these are not attracted by cattle & wild animal.
9. Children and old persons of rear's family can also participate in the rearing process.
10. Eri culture helps in enhancing economic status of rural rearers.
11. It is women's friendly and ecofriendly occupation.
12. There is practically no risk in the industry.

Weakness: -

1. Unpredictable rainfall and reducing ground water level effects plantation.
2. Climatic condition is another barrier of sericulture.
3. There is resistance in rural masses to adopt new technologies for sericulture.
4. The rearers have small land holding for rearing.
5. There is lack of competitive marketing network.
6. There is no proper organization for collecting Cocoon and Seed distribution.
7. Management of the Sericulture forms is poor.

Opportunities: -

1. Eri culture sector includes active involvement of rural women.
2. The demand for silk is growing in the national & international market day by day because of its qualities.
3. Due to awareness in education in rural areas, literate farmers are willing to accept latest technological knowhow.
4. It holds promise as an employment generating industry, especially in rural and semi-urban areas.
5. It gives an additional source of income to agriculture and rural population.

Threats: -

1. More and more rural population is migrating from farming to urban areas.
2. Other agriculture crops like wheat, grain etc are competitive crops.
3. Eri silk has to face compete with the synthetic fiber because of its low cost.
4. Majority of farmers have low land holding capacity.
5. The cost of the land is very high.
6. SWOT analysis is to develop work plan for research that takes into consideration many different internal and external factors and maximizes the potential of the strengths and opportunities while seeking minimize the impact of the weaknesses and threats.

CONCLUSION

SWOT analysis is a systematic identification and strategic decision making operation. SWOT analysis of Eri culture for Ujjain District in reference to sustainable development of rearers and promote development of the silk industry by all appropriate measures and for this purpose in particular. SWOT analysis is reducing gap among scientist, experts, sericulture's and artisans. However, the gap between them cannot be eliminated unless social workers and Voluntary organization act as a link.

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